

BUILDING THE SOFT SKILLS OF STUDENTS IN FORTREPIANO LESSONS

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Abstract: This article contains opinions on the formation of soft skills of secondary school students in music culture lessons. Also, information about the importance and effectiveness of soft skills in the education system is presented. What is "Soft Skills" is also explained.

Key words: "Soft skills", music culture, pedagogue, secondary school students, national personnel training program, art.

Comprehensive updates and positive changes are being implemented in the education system as well as in all areas in our country. The Law "On Education" "National Personnel Training Program" serves as a legal and organizational pedagogical basis for this. Along with updating and improving the content of education and increasing the quality indicators, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers-trainers, to keep them in step with the development of science and science, especially those who can effectively use information technologies and interactive methods, which are widely used in all fields. One of the important tasks of today is training (re-training) to the level of being able to freely communicate with the computer and to be able to apply it in one's work to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson.

In increasing the effectiveness of the teaching process, the introduction of "soft skills" technologies into education and their skillful use are important. After all, in traditional education, students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, according to the criteria of developmental education, students can learn, analyze, and draw conclusions by themselves. becomes important with its direction. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of the educational system organized in the educational institutions of higher pedagogics to enable the future teachers to use soft skills in their activities, and to apply them creatively and freely in practice. .

What are "soft skills"? What is its role in personal development?

No person can live without society. The members of the society enter into various relations under different conditions. A significant part of these relations corresponds to the work and labor process. When a specialist who has graduated from a higher educational institution enters the labor market, is the

knowledge he received at an educational institution enough for him to get a decent job and achieve the desired career? Of course not. The reason for this is that knowledge in the subjects taught at the educational institution is obtained as a result of mastering certain facts, databases and their analysis. However, they do not fully cover the issues of establishing interpersonal relationships. However, in today's globalized and market economy-based society, employers pay attention to the extent to which they are able to establish interpersonal relationships. They know very well that it is through this feature that the company can develop, justify the trust of customers and achieve an increase in their number.

"Soft skills" is a system of skills and abilities necessary to organize and conduct interpersonal relations in a correct and purposeful manner. Such qualifications and skills are also called "life skills". As a person develops these skills and abilities, his personal development increases.

Modernization of the organization of the educational process and the implementation of its innovative forms and methods in order to achieve the quality and efficiency indicators envisaged at the crucial stage of the implementation of the national personnel training program cannot be delayed today. is an urgent issue. Therefore, the question of what are the object, subject, goals and tasks of advanced pedagogical technologies and what results will their application in the educational process give and how will it affect the improvement of educational content? It is not for nothing that it is being used. The incredibly fast and intense development process of science, technology and information transmission and exchange technologies, in turn, requires enrichment with "Soft skills" methods in the field of education. So, what aspects of the use of "soft skills" are gaining advantage? What are its types, structural structure, forms and means of organizing educational processes, how does it differ from previously existing teaching (Education) methods, what are its results and how is its monitoring carried out? It is necessary to realize that every student-mentor and pedagogue is ready for questions and answer these questions.

The education of students of Music Culture in general secondary schools serves to form human spirituality. After all, it is important because it forms the level of musical culture. Culture as an indicator of spirituality is a broad concept and one of the most controversial issues. Middle school students of general secondary education have the opportunity to form "soft skills", which help to form students' thinking, imagining, feeling and other abilities. It should be noted

here that soft skills are one of the most effective pedagogical technologies in the educational system. Due to the correct establishment of musical culture, a person develops certain musical knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities, which in turn form the musical and spiritual outlook of a person. A person's musical culture is manifested in a set of qualities such as ability, knowledge, skills, ability to evaluate musical works, and serves as a factor of spiritual growth. Therefore, it is appropriate to start this type of education from the family first of all. Later, this process is improved in secondary school, secondary special and higher stages of education.

Of course, the subject of music culture at school serves as a basis for the composition of musical culture. This course also has historical significance in the field of music work with children. It is clear that only a method that has a solid scientific basis, is used in wide practice, has been tested and, at the same time, is constantly being improved. A music teacher should know the characteristics and capabilities of students of each class. It is known that "methodology" is such a part of pedagogy that, on the basis of didactic principles, with the help of a method, the educational process is carried out appropriately and its general and special tasks are solved. For example, how to achieve the educational effect of music, to arouse the interest of students, to organize listening to music for students of junior and middle grades, and to achieve the competence of active perception of students. At the same time, the methodology also covers specific issues. In the methodology of music education, it is emphasized that the educational process, like any social activity, requires systematic and scientific management.

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